

Path of Miracles: a Multitrack Recording in 3D Audio to Recreate and Study Choral Blending

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In late August of 2022, the rich sonority of the historical Chapelle du Grand Séminaire de Montréal presented the acoustical canvas for a multifaceted choral recording and research project. Under the baton of Andrew Gray, Montreal choir Voces Boreales performed Joby Talbot's *Path of Miracles* for mixed chorus (2005) and percussion, a musical pilgrimage for 17 voices, inspired by the millennial Camino de Santiago de Compostela.

Principal Investigator and Tonmeister Martha de Francisco directed the production using a precisely finetuned immersive multichannel recording set-up for 7.1.4 that included close and diffuse elements. PhD researcher Ying-Ying Zhang was in charge of implementing experimental spatial audio capture systems, including two comparative systems for capturing height and bottom layer reproduction and two second-order Ambisonics positions accompanied by 360-degree video. They were aided by a team that included graduate students from McGill University's Sound Recording program, who assisted and visually documented the process.

The resulting recording serves multiple purposes, including a release in stereo and immersive sound as well as a sound installation that occurred at St. James United Church in downtown Montreal in June 2023. The extensive repository of recorded tracks will remain accessible to the ACTOR community. It will be at the center of choral blending research studies and expert aural analysis and comparative evaluations at the HfM Detmold and at McGill University, which will lead to future research outputs.

An immersive sound system in high-definition audio has been designed to record Voces Boreales from different perspectives, using 38 professional studio microphones (see schematic diagram below). When mixed, the various layers of sound present a vibrant and complete sonic picture of the performance. Using 3D recording techniques, a complex array of 7 omnidirectional microphones, placed in front of the choir in different distances and heights, is complemented by an immersive sound capture system of 6 omnidirectional microphones aimed at providing envelopment and a sense of integration of the acoustics. 18 cardioid microphones in the close range, one for each singer, as well as a stereo capture for the percussion instruments (bells and crotales), brings additionally a detailed close perspective of the individual musicians. This forms the basis for the sound of the installation staged at St. James United Church, a technical system for the performance of the recording by using 18+6 loudspeakers reproducing virtually the presence of the musicians performing the work.

Below you will find various photos taken during the recording session, which give a general impression of the microphone placement and physical dimensions of the recording space. In addition, the microphone placement schematic below contains links to learn more about the microphones used and how they were placed, and by clicking each link you can also hear an excerpt of the recording captured with those microphones only. In addition, a mastered final mix of Movement IV (Santiago) of *Path of Miracles* is available to stream below (MP3).

<https://tinyurl.com/3b2hyhst>

Credits

Path of Miracles (Jody Talbot, 2005)

Recorded at The Chapelle du Grand Seminaire de Montréal, August 26–28, 2022

- *PI, record producer, Tonmeister*: Martha de Francisco
- *Performers*: Voces Boreales, directed by Andrew Gray
- *Collaborators*: Stratsimir Dimitrov and Ying-Ying Zhang
- *ACTOR Students*: Marco Petrella and Mathieu Blanchet
- *ACTOR Partner (Detmold)*: Michael Sandner

Microphone Placement

The below schematic details the microphones used and their placement in the recording space.

Legend:

- OL/OR:** Outrigger left and right
- HL/HR:** Heights left and right
- DA/DB/DC:** Decca Tree
- SL/SR:** Surround left and right
- RHL/RHR:** Rear heights left and right

Spot Microphones (Neumann KM184)

In the context of acoustic recording, spot microphones capture individual sound sources. When mixed with microphones that capture the main image of the recording and the reverberation of the room, spots provide a sense of clarity and bring the performers closer to the listening position. If they are too low in the mix, listeners may feel a sense of fatigue as if they cannot quite hear a far-away voice. If they are too high, it may instead give the impression that the listener is being shouted at from a close distance. The Neumann KM184 microphone is a small diaphragm condenser microphone often used in classical music applications. Its small diaphragm capture provides a relatively fast transient response, and the cardioid pickup pattern provides some rejection of the room while making relatively small compromises on frequency response. While microphones were placed to capture as much of every individual voice while rejecting nearby sound sources, there is still bleed between capture points, with some positions rejecting more than others.

Decca Tree (DPA 4006)

Designed for large ensemble recordings, the Decca Tree (named for the eponymous record company) comprises widely spaced A and B microphones with a center fill (C). The system's wide stance allows for the maximum amount of decorrelation between a left side (A) and a right side (B) stereo signal, while still coherent enough for the listener to identify them as part of the same image. The Decca C position anchors the image's central position while providing greater compatibility with multichannel playback systems that have a standalone center speaker (rather than relying on the phantom center image of two-channel stereo). The DPA 4006 microphone is a small diaphragm condenser with an exceptionally flat frequency response. Originally developed by B&K as a measurement microphone, the 4006's omnidirectional pickup pattern stems from its fixed pressure capsule. Omnidirectional microphones are more sensitive to low frequencies than directional microphones, making them the most complete single-point capsule. Not only is the DPA 4006 favoured by classical engineers on Earth, but NASA's Perseverance rover was also equipped with a 4006 on its 2020 mission, making it the favourite microphone on Mars.

Outrigger Left and Right (DPA 4006)

Named for the lateral support floats that project from certain types of boats, outrigger microphones bolster the far left and right sides of an image, allowing it to extend further without capsizing. The positions of the soprano and bass voices from this recording extended well into the pews on either side of the church, making them difficult to capture with the Decca Tree. While spot microphones can capture each singer's individual voice, they are not ideal for capturing the blended sound of the entire section. Outriggers are often the same type of microphone as the main system, and function in a similar way. The DPA 4006 microphone is a small diaphragm condenser with an exceptionally flat frequency response. Originally developed by B&K as a measurement microphone, the 4006's omnidirectional pickup pattern stems from its fixed pressure capsule. Omnidirectional microphones are more sensitive to low frequencies than directional microphones, making them the most complete single-point capsule. Not only is the DPA 4006 favoured by classical engineers on Earth, but NASA's Perseverance rover was also equipped with a 4006 on its 2020 mission, making it the favourite microphone on Mars.

Height Left and Right (DPA 4006)

The Height Left and Height Right microphones were placed in the same lateral position as the A and B microphones of the Decca Tree but were raised one meter higher. In order to obtain information for the current standard of multichannel reproduction (7.1.4), acoustic information from above the listening position is captured in order to offer a more complete and immersive experience of the performance. This information must be perceptually decorrelated from the main image and contain more reverberant and less direct sound, otherwise the listener may find that the entire ensemble now sounds as though they are singing in the rafters. The DPA 4006 microphone is a small diaphragm condenser with an exceptionally flat frequency response. Originally developed by B&K as a measurement microphone, the 4006's omnidirectional pickup pattern stems from its fixed pressure capsule. Omnidirectional microphones are more sensitive to low frequencies than directional microphones, making them the most complete single-point capsule. Not only is the DPA 4006 favoured by classical engineers on Earth, but NASA's Perseverance rover was also equipped with a 4006 on its 2020 mission, making it the favourite microphone on Mars.

Surround Left and Right (DPA 4006)

Surround Left and Surround Right microphones were placed 2.5 meters behind the main Decca Tree system and another 0.5m higher in elevation. Much like the movies, audio information from surround capture points provides mostly ambience, while the main action happens in the front of the space. In the stereo recording, these sources were mixed into the left and the right as room reverb, but in the multichannel reproduction, these channels provide a sense of acoustic space that extends behind the listener, mimicking the feeling of the church's long, rectangular shape. The DPA 4006 microphone is a small diaphragm condenser with an exceptionally flat frequency response. Originally developed by B&K as a measurement microphone, the 4006's omnidirectional pickup pattern stems from its fixed pressure capsule. Omnidirectional microphones are more sensitive to low frequencies than directional microphones, making them the most complete single-point capsule. Not only is the DPA 4006 favoured by classical engineers on Earth, but NASA's Perseverance rover was also equipped with a 4006 on its 2020 mission, making it the favourite microphone on Mars.

Rear Height Left and Right (Schoeps MK2H)

At a staggering 5 meters in height and 3 meters further back than the surround system, the Rear Height microphones had to be placed on specially extended stands. This system captured the most decorrelated sound from the frontal image of the performers and was positioned to capture the extended ambience reverberating towards the ceiling of the church with minimal direct sound. While generally flat, omnidirectional microphones become increasingly directional in higher frequencies, so this is an often-used technique to draw attention toward or away from certain sound sources. The Schoeps MK2H microphone features a slight boost in frequencies above 6kHz. This purposeful coloration helps distinguish the surround capture system from the Decca Tree and other front-facing capture systems. It is also in a relatively meaningful range for human hearing, which is focused on mid to high frequencies.